

CLINICAL, INSTRUMENTAL AND PROGNOSTIC ASPECTS OF GASTROINTESTINAL DYSFUNCTIONS IN EARLY-AGE CHILDREN WITH PERINATAL INJURY OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Background: Perinatal central nervous system injury (PCNSI) is a significant risk factor for the development of functional gastrointestinal disorders in infants, contributing to complex neuro-vegetative and visceral dysfunctions during early life.

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Aim: To identify the clinical and instrumental characteristics of functional gastrointestinal disorders in children under one year of age with PCNSI and to develop criteria for their early diagnosis.

Methods: The study included 32 children aged 1 month to 1 year who received inpatient treatment. Physical development was assessed using anthropometric indicators in accordance with WHO (2006) standards. All patients underwent neurosonographic examination, and gastrointestinal status was evaluated using clinical, laboratory, and instrumental methods, including abdominal ultrasound. Maternal, perinatal, and intranatal risk factors, as well as neurological and veeto-visceral dysfunctions, were analyzed. Statistical analysis was performed using parametric and correlation methods, with significance set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: Functional gastrointestinal disorders were identified in all examined children: unspecified functional disturbances in 35% of cases, functional diarrhea in 30%, and constipation in 35%. Veeto-visceral dysfunctions were observed universally and correlated with the severity of PCNSI. Perinatal hypoxia and autonomic imbalance were found to play a key role in the development of gastrointestinal dysfunctions. Ultrasound examination proved to be a highly informative method for early detection of functional gastrointestinal abnormalities.

Conclusion: Gastrointestinal disorders develop early and progress rapidly in children with PCNSI, forming a complex clinical picture. The proposed diagnostic criteria enable timely identification of gastrointestinal and neurological complications, optimization of therapeutic

strategies, and reduction of treatment costs, thereby improving both clinical outcomes and economic efficiency.

